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Imports of Goods and Services in Europe

Between 2010 and 2021 they grew by 59.33%

Eurostat calculates the value of imports of goods and services. Data are available between 2010 and 2021. Data are expressed in millions of euros.

Ranking of countries by value of imports of goods and services in 2021. Germany ranks first by value of imports with a value of €1,502,370 million, followed by France with a value of €785,046 million, and from the Netherlands with a value of 622,743 million euros. Halfway through the table are Romania with a value of €111,693.90 million, Finland with a value of €98,505 million, and Portugal with a value of €95,604.50 million. The ranking is closed by Albania with a value equal to 6,776.70 million euros, by Kosovo with a value equal to 5,190.90 million euros and by Montenegro with a value equal to 3,081.90 million euros.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage change in imports of goods and services between 2010 and 2021. Ireland is in first place by the value of the percentage change in imports of goods and services with a value equal to 179.19% equal to an amount of 260,003.40 million euros, followed by Estonia with a value of 144.50% equal to an amount of 14,618.30 million euros and by Serbia with a value equal to 136.73% equal to an amount of 19,182.80 million euros. In the middle of the table are the Czech Republic with a value equal to 68.45% equal to an amount of 67,540.70 million euros, followed by Denmark with a value equal to 66.90% equal to a value of 70,886.20 million euros and from Turkey with a value equal to 64.28% equal to an amount of 95,868.80 million euros. The ranking is closed by Greece with a value equal to 33.96% equal to an amount of 22,379.50 million euros, followed by Norway with a value equal to 29.52% equal to an amount of 27,230.70 million euros and from Italy with a variation of 24.48% equal to an amount of 106,246.60 million euros.

Ranking of countries by level of exports as a percentage of imports between 2010 and 2021. Norway ranks first in value of exports as a percentage of imports between 2010 and 2021 with a value of 41.81% equal to a amount of 49,952 million euros, followed by Ireland with a value equal to 41.44% equal to an amount of 167,885.50 million euros, and by Switzerland with a value equal to 19.99% equal to an amount of 80,480 60 million euros. In the middle of the table are Belgium with a value equal to 1.23% equal to an amount of 5,281.60 million euros, followed by Austria with a value equal to 1.05% equal to an amount of 2,348.90 million euros, and from Finland with a value equal to 0.58% equal to an amount of 576 million euros. Albania closes the ranking with a value equal to -30.26% equivalent to a trade surplus of -2,050.80 million euros, followed by Montenegro with 31.31% equal to an amount of -959.4 million euro, and from Kosovo with a value equal to -48.78% equal to an amount of -2,532.20 million euro.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The analysis shows the presence of two clusters as indicated below, namely:

- Cluster 1: Belgium, Spain, Switzerland, Ireland, Poland, Turkey, Sweden, Austria, Denmark, Czech Republic, Norway, Montenegro, Hungary, Kosovo, Albania, North Macedonia, Iceland, Luxembourg, Bosnia, Finland, Cyprus, Malta , Romania, Portugal, Latvia, Estonia, Slovakia, Greece, Serbia, Croatia, Lithuania, Slovenia, Bulgaria;

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- Cluster 2: France, Germany, Netherlands, Italy.

From the point of view of the median, it appears that the median value of cluster 2-C2 is equal to 703,894.50 million euros, while the median value of cluster 1-C1 is equal to 92,637.4 million euros. It therefore follows that $C2 > C1$.

Network Analysis with Manhattan distance. By applying the network analysis through the distance of Manhattan it is possible to identify a set of both simplified and complex structures. There is a complex network structure present between Lithuania, Bulgaria, and Slovenia. Particularly:

- Lithuania has a connection with Slovenia worth 0.021 and with Bulgaria worth 0.017;
- Bulgaria has a connection with Lithuania worth 0.02 and with Slovenia worth 0.017;
- Slovenia has a connection with Bulgaria with a value of 0.017 and with Lithuania with a value of 0.021.

There is a connection between Kosovo, Montenegro, Albania, Iceland, North Macedonia, Bosnia. Particularly:

- Bosnia has a connection with North Macedonia worth 0.022, with Iceland worth 0.017, and with Albania worth 0.032.
- North Macedonia has a connection with Ireland worth 0.01, with Albania worth 0.014, with Bosnia worth 0.022 and with Kosovo worth value equal to 0.031 units;
- Iceland has a connection with North Macedonia for a value of 0.01 units, with Albania for a value equal to 0.021 units, with Bosnia for a value equal to 0.017 units;
- Albania has a connection with Iceland for a value equal to 0.021 units, with North Macedonia for a value equal to 0.014 units with Bosnia for a value equal to 0.032, with Kosovo for a value equal to 0.019 units, with Montenegro for a value equal to 0.026 units;
- Kosovo has a connection with Albania for a value equal to 0.019 units, with Montenegro for a value equal to 0.007 units, with North Macedonia for a value equal to 0.031 units;
- Montenegro has a connection with Kosovo worth 0.07 and with Albania worth 0.026.

There is a complex network structure consisting of Latvia, Malta, Estonia, and Cyprus. Particularly:

- Latvia has a connection with Cyprus equal to a value of 0.026 units, with Malta for a value equal to 0.019 units, with Estonia for a value equal to 0.0063 units;
- Malta has a connection with Latvia for a value of 0.019 units, with Estonia for a value equal to 0.023 units and with Cyprus for a value equal to 0.012 units;
- Cyprus has a connection with Malta with a value of 0.012 units, with Estonia with a value of 0.031 units and with Latvia with a value of 0.023 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Latvia equal to 0.0063 units, with Malta equal to 0.026 units and with Cyprus equal to 0.031 units.

There is also a simplified network structure, i.e.:

- Croatia and Serbia have a connection equal to a value of 0.019 units.

Conclusions. the value of imports grew between 2010 and 2021 from an amount of 205,946.24 million euros up to a value of 129,256.88 million euros or equal to a change of 76,689.35 million euros equal to an amount of 59.33%. However, between 2019 and 2020 the value of imports decreased from an amount of 194,458.21 million euros down to a value of 175,613.16 million euros or equal to a value of -18,845.05 million euros equal to a value of -9.69%. The growth of imports could decrease in the future due to a combination of factors including: reduction of the value of the euro, Russian-

Ukrainian conflict, trade tension between Europe and the United States, and Sino-American techwar. In fact, the devaluation of the Euro, due to the continuous post-covid expansionary monetary policies, makes imports from the USA and UK more expensive. On the other hand, the tension between the USA and China also puts imports from Asia in difficulty. Finally, trade relations between the USA and Europe are also subject to significant political tensions with reference to raw materials and the energy sector. However, the devaluation of the euro could push the European economy to resume the production of goods and services and to reduce offshoring and friend-shoring operations with the aim of increasing exports. A possibility which, however, could encounter the limitations of import taxes which could lead international trade into a new phase of protectionism.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l., prof. Alberto Costantiello and prof. Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

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Appendix

